

Exploring Teachers' Belief toward Teaching Language Features of Genres on K13 Curriculum

Ahmat Rondi Toyib¹ and Achmad Anang Darmawan²

English Language Education
STKIP Al Hikmah
Surabaya, Indonesia
toyibalba30@gmail.com¹

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Abstract: The objectives of this research are to reveal the teachers' point of view, describe the teachers' practices, and to investigate the factors which influence teachers' beliefs toward teaching language features of genres on K13. The research method used in this research is descriptive using qualitative approach. The procedures of the research were using four steps, such as pre-research, data collection, data analysis, and writing a report. The subjects of the research were three English teachers from the same school who are teaching in SMPN 21 Surabaya at the 7th and 8th grades using K13. The researcher conducted three steps in collecting data, such as observations, interviews, documentation. The result of the research are the teachers believed that they have to teach language features of genres to their students, drilling is still relevant to be applied, the way of teaching was adjusted due to the condition of the classroom. In their teaching and learning process, all teachers were teaching language features of genres using conventional ways, such as the teachers were only using a textbook as the main guidance in teaching, the teachers were handling all the learning activities, and the teachers did not guide the students to reflect what they had learned in that day as the goal of the implementation of K13. Then, that all teachers' teaching practices were consistent to their beliefs were influenced by their experience as language learners, experience of what works best, personality factors, and principles derived from an approach or method.

Keywords: *teachers' beliefs, language features of genres, K13*

INTRODUCTION

There were three objectives in this research. The first, it aimed to reveal the teachers' point of view toward teaching language features of genres on K13. The second, it described the teachers' practices toward teaching language features of genres on K13. Third, it investigated the factors which influence teachers' beliefs toward teaching language features of genres on K13. The researcher conducted the research both in 7th and 8th grade classrooms of SMPN 21 Surabaya. The research was conducted for about two weeks, starting from January 14th up to February 1st, 2019. It involved one 7th grade English teacher and two 8th grade English teachers. The subjects involved in this research are three English teachers who one teacher is teaching in 7th grade and another two are teaching in 8th grade. Their initial names were written as RA, ER, and YA. All of them are female English teachers who graduated on English Education Department. Moreover, all three teachers have been teaching for more than ten years and their teaching duration is about 30 hours in a week. In this case, the teachers are assumed that they have enough experience in teaching and their beliefs are resistant to change.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Definition of Belief

Pajares (1992) viewed beliefs as individual's decisions of the reality. In this case, beliefs are related to personal perspective. It is in line with Richardson's opinion (1996) that defined belief as thoughts that held understandings about something are perceived to be true. From those studies, beliefs might either be true or false among different person.

Moreover, Hinkel and Fotos (2001) defined belief as an attitude consistently applied to an activity. It means that if what people believe valued to be good, they will be committed to do it. Borg (2011) stated that beliefs are propositions which people consider to be true and which are often unspoken, have a strong evaluative and affective component, provide basis for action, and resistant to change. He added that beliefs are seen to be a key of element in teachers' learning and have become an important focus

for research. Therefore, since beliefs of people are strong and difficult to change, it is interested the researcher to conduct a research to explore whether people's beliefs are changed after perceiving a new insight.

Teachers and Their Beliefs

Teachers have a great responsibility to design the teaching methods to be implemented in the classroom. They sometimes have planned various teaching methods to their lesson plan which have been perceived from the applied curriculum to fulfill their students' needs. When the teachers believed that such teaching method is suitable to be practiced in teaching, they will commit to do it repeatedly. It will also become their basis to make a decision. It is line with Gilakjani and Sabouri (2017) that beliefs play a key role in teachers' knowledge on making a lesson plan, including the decisions made and the classroom activities. In teaching and learning process, beliefs have affected on teachers' practices. Based on Phipps and Borg (2009), the influences of teachers' beliefs about teaching and learning are (1) have a significant influence on teachers' way of teaching (2) strongly influence what and how teachers learn during language teacher education (3) can be strongly-shaped behaviour on teachers'and resistant to change. Teachers' beliefs have greater effect than the teachers' knowledge on Gilakjani and Sabouri (2017). They added that the teachers' beliefs will identify the teachers' real behaviour toward their learners. Since beliefs shaped teachers' personal knowledge and beliefs consisted of perspective problems, decision, and significant teaching experience, it explains how and why different teachers have different reasons for selecting a specific materials, different ways of teaching at the same materials, different styles of teaching, and different modes of learning (Zain and Rohani, 2007). So, the diversity on the teachers' perceptions was influenced by their beliefs.

In the moment-to-moment existence of practices, teachers frequently relied on their beliefs which were particularly underlied the perception and habit to meet the demands of practice (Fives and Gill, 2015). If teachers' beliefs in teaching are in line with what is supposed to be implemented in such a particular school, it is supposed to help the teachers to design an interesting activities in the teaching and learning process

in the classroom. Otherwise, if teachers' beliefs were not suitable with the implemented curriculum, they will mismatch in their teaching practices (Farahian, 2011).

According to Borg (2003), teachers' beliefs are usually used to refer to teachers' thoughts about teaching and learning, such as views of language teaching, learning and teaching beliefs, curriculum perspective, and views on learners and teachers. So, teachers' beliefs can be seen when on the way of teachers teaching in the classroom. It is in line with Wafa, Fauziati, and Hikmat (2016) that teachers' beliefs are such a fundamental basis of understanding the teachers' perspectives on the teaching. Therefore, to see that teachers' beliefs really influenced their teaching practices, a survey to teachers' beliefs and the an exploration toward their practices are very needed.

According to Zain and Rohani (2007), one of the focus on teachers' beliefs is beliefs about grammar teaching and learning. Regarding about the recent issues about the implementation of K13 that grammar teaching and learning should be no longer taught, the researcher are encouraged to conduct a research on this field. The research will focus on exploring teachers' beliefs about teaching language features of genres as a part of grammar teaching and learning, especially on the implementation of K13.

The Source of Beliefs

According to Richards, Jack, and Lockhart (1994), there are six sources of teachers' beliefs, such as: their own experience as language learners; experience of what works best; established practice; personality factors; educationally based or research-based principles; and principles derived from an approach or method. The source of teachers' beliefs are explained as the following:

- Teachers' beliefs come from their own experience as language learners.
- Teachers' beliefs come from their experience of what work best.
- Teachers' beliefs come from established practices.
- Teachers' beliefs come from personality factors.
- Teachers' beliefs come from educationally based or research-based principles.
- Teachers' beliefs come from principles derived from an approach or method.

Teaching Language Features of Genres

To ease the way of teaching language features of genres in the classroom, the government should provide some various methods. Unfortunately, the unclear regulation toward the way of teaching language features of genres on K13 makes the teachers interpret the way of teaching language features of genres depend on their beliefs. However, teachers' beliefs may not always be reflected in their instructional decisions when teaching language features of genres in their actual classroom practices (Farrell and Lim, 2005; Alghanmi and Shukri, 2016). So, a mismatch often occurs between the teachers' beliefs and their practices. The mismatch could be resulted from the clash between two major beliefs in teaching language features of genres, they are: explicit teaching and implicit teaching. Ling (2015) defined explicit learning refers to learning language features of genres and vocabulary while implicit learning refers to making conclusion toward what they are currently learning about. Although, the curriculum may mandate to language features of genres explicitly, while teachers believe in teaching language features of genres implicitly, or vice versa. In contrast, the curriculum has restricted to teach grammar in context, but the teachers are still teaching language features of genres (Farahian, 2011).

Based on the previous studies conducted by Farrell and Lim (2005), Alghanmi and Shukri (2016), and Farahian (2011), there some mismatches occur because of the differences between the teachers' beliefs and what is expected by the curriculum. So, it needs more explorations whether most of the teachers are following the curriculum or they have their own ways which are implemented in the classroom. Therefore, the researcher wants to explore teachers' beliefs towards their teaching practices.

The Implementation of K13

In Indonesian educational system, there have been some changes on the applied curricula. It was because of curriculum in education has a dynamic characteristic and it can be changed based on the education necessity (Khasanah and Widyanoro, 2013), such as to build students' characters, tolerance, empathy (Fauzi, 2014). Aside, Ekawati (2016) explained that the curricula were changed because of many factors, like the

changes of students' needs, the new model of teaching learning process, political issues, the development of industry and technology. She added that the objective of curriculum changes is to improve the quality of education.

As the answer of what stated in the previous paragraph, the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture Regulation 2018 implemented K13 as the school curriculum since the academic year 2014/2015 (Kemendikbud, 2018). Since then, the K13 was implemented in some schools. K13 was designed for welcoming the learning model in the 21st century in which the students are expected to find out the learning material through any sources (Kemendikbud, 2018). Aside, K13 also demands the learners to acquire the 21st century skills, including 4Cs, such as critical thinking and problem solving, collaboration, creativity, and communication (Kemendikbud, 2018). Besides, the objective of curriculum includes four competences, like spiritual, social, cognitive, and skills in which the students can gain them through curricular program, such as intra-curricular, co-curricular, and/or extra-curricular. Thus, it can be concluded that the implementation of K13 is hoped to improve the education quality in which emphasizes on student-centered learning.

Teaching English Based on K13

The main goal of English teaching and learning is to improve students' competence to mastering English as a tool for communication (Kemendikbud, 2018). It means that the main focus of teaching English is to train students to use language to communicate effectively. It is in line with Nur and Madkur (2014) that the final goal of English teaching is the proficiency of students' communication skills using English language. They also proposed some principles of teaching English based K13 related to use English as tool of communication, such as: students learn English by using scientific approach including observing, questioning, exploring, associating, and communicating. Then, students are expected to learn English for communication through activities, real text, and using the language. Therefore, the main goal of teaching English based K13 is to enable students to master and use English in their daily communication.

Teaching Language Features of Genres on K13

Based on the Core Competence and Basic Competence issued by Kemendikbud (2014), the way of teaching language features of genres on K13 is not explicitly mentioned. It only emphasizes on that in learning English students are able to use English as a language to communicate in daily life. As written on the Training of the K13 Implementation Module, English language learning is focused on genre-based text. The goal of learning genre-based text is to develop students' communication skills to use and apply the social function of each genre-based text in daily life (Kemendikbud, 2018). The genre-based text is learned on its three aspects, such as the social function, generic structures of the text, language features. Since the way of teaching language features of genres in K13 was not clearly stated on the government's regulation, teachers are given opportunities to design the teaching and learning process by their own way. Considering the purpose of learning English is to enable students to use English as a language for communication in daily life, the teachers should be implicitly teaching language features of genres rather than correct their tenses.

The Way of Teaching Language Features of Genres

The way of teaching language features of genres was not clearly stated on K13. The. So, the teachers have their own way of teaching language features of genres. Based on the previous research conducted by Thu (2009) found that teaching language features of genres is supposed to the finally acquiring a foreign or second language. So, he believed that language features of genres should be taught explicitly, not implicitly.

Whether teachers teaching language features of genres explicitly or implicitly, they were influenced by their beliefs. One of explicit methods which is still practiced by most teachers in teaching language features is drilling. Fransiska (2016) stated that the use of drilling technique can help students' mastering vocabulary. Then, drilling technique was also applied to improve students' speaking ability (Khetaguri and Albay, 2016; Alawiyah, 2017). While, Maharida (2014) said that the use of substitution drill was effective to improve students' pronunciation ability. They believed that drilling is still

relevant to be practiced in the classroom. Although, teachers also can use other ways of their teaching, such as using games and song. According to Claudia Perse (2018, August 11), games can be involved as an innovation to language features of genres as. Moreover, Ambarini and Wilujeng (2012), was integrating language features of genres teaching with an inspiring song and game-based lesson. They believe that it will help to enhance the students' understanding the language and learning the English language.

Based on the explanations above, there are many ways in teaching language features of genres in order to fulfil the students' needs. Therefore, it is important for the teachers to design the way of teaching language features of genres implicitly in order to ease the understanding of the students to use language as tool for communication.

METHODOLOGY

The design of this research was descriptive using qualitative approach. The qualitative approach used during this research was applied to the data collection techniques which the researcher didn't give any treatment in exploring teachers' beliefs and it ran naturally. According to Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2014), qualitative research is conducted through both seriously and sustainable interaction with subjects in a natural setting to investigate the daily activities of individual groups, societies, and organizations. Therefore, in the process of collecting the data, such as observations, interviews, and documentation didn't influenced the natural setting of exploring teachers' beliefs.

The procedure in this research was divided into four steps, such as pre-research, data collection, data analysis, and report writing.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

Based on the questionnaires, the teachers' beliefs toward teaching language features of genres on K13 are discussed as the following: (1) All teachers believed that teaching language features of genres is important and they have to teach them. They believed that teaching language features of genres will help students to understand the use of English language, nurture the students to understand the correct English, and help

students to understand the grammar and the structures. (2) One of three teachers believed that students need to know language features of genres while 2 of them didn't. One teacher believed that by knowing the language features of genres the students can know the the time signal used in a sentence. Two other teachers disagreed because when all students should understand the language features of genres, the process of teaching and learning will not run well. Then, the students only have to know the language features of genres, but not to understand them deeply. (3) Two of three teachers believed that drilling is an effective method to teach students language features of genres. Two teachers believed that by using drilling, the students will help students to always remember the pronunciation of the words and it will train the students to keep using the language for communication. One other teacher disagreed that drilling will be useless if the students keep making mistakes.

(4) All teachers believed that language features of genres focused on correct tenses. The believed that it will help the students to make the correct sentences and differentiate the use of the tenses in the correct time, such as past tense, present tense, and future tense.

(5) All teachers believed that in teaching language features of genres, they are teaching language structures, especially in the 7th grade. (6) Two of three teachers believed that the teachers should teach language features of genres as a part of effective methods in the classroom. Two teachers believed that they have to teach the 7th the three basic tense only, such as present, past, and future by analyzing some sentences from a passage while one other teacher was focused on finishing all the targeted materials in a semester.

(7) Two of three teachers believed that there is a place for conscious teaching language features of genres to enable students to acquire language skills. Two teachers believed that they can teach language features of genres in the process of teaching and learning, such as when giving them some instructions. Moreover, they can also give some opportunities to the students to have a consultation out of the teaching and learning process. One other teacher disagreed that there was a program to train the students to use the language, but it didn't run well. (8) Two of three teachers believed that the approach in teaching language features of genres depends on the students' English

proficiency. One teacher believed that the students should really master the particular material learned instead of finishing all materials during a semester and one other teacher believed that it will help the effectiveness of teaching and learning process by jig-saw method. Then, one other teacher disagreed that the teacher should use the different technique based on the condition of the classroom.

Based on the data collection gained, including questionnaires, interview transcripts, and observation field notes, it is shown that teachers' practices toward teaching language features of genres on K13 is consistent with their beliefs. (1) Based on the questionnaire, they believed that in teaching language features of genres, they should teach language structure. Based on the observation, they taught tenses as the main materials in a meeting, those were Simple Present and Past Continuous. (2) They believed that language features of genres is important and need to be taught, so they taught language features of genres in the classroom. From the observation, they were teaching language features, including explaining the pattern, analyzing the subject and verb, defining time signal.

(4) They believed that the students should know the language features of genres and how to apply them in making sentences. In their teaching, they all explained about the subject, the verb, and the time signal. They also explained the students when they should match either the subject with the verb or the verb with the time signal. (5) They believed that in teaching language features of genres, they would concerned with the correct tenses. During the lesson, the teachers corrected the students' work whether what they wrote on the whiteboard or the task which they submitted to the teachers.

(6) Two teachers (RA & YA) believed that drilling is a useful method in teaching language features of genres, but one teacher (ER) believed that drilling is just useless when the students often make mistakes due to their language proficiency. At the time, they just focused on writing skill, so they didn't drill the students about language features of genres. (7) They believed that the approach applied in the classroom was adjusted due to the condition of the class and it should not be applied thoroughly as it

stated in K13. In the end of the lesson, scientific approach in K13 was not well-applied in the classroom, but the teachers were consistent to apply their beliefs to their practices.

From the data, all teachers' practices were consistent to their beliefs in most aspects stated in the questionnaire. Because, the observations were just conducted once for each teacher, their beliefs about using drilling as a method in teaching language features weren't be able to be explored. Nevertheless, most of the findings strongly support the consistency of teachers' practices toward their beliefs. Moreover, there are some factors which influenced teachers toward teaching language features of genres on K13 explained as the following:

(1) Experience as language learners

All teachers were taught language features of genres, such as Tenses which was learning about the patterns and make some examples. Moreover, the way of teaching was using drilling method. This way was also applied when the teachers were teaching language features of genres. Two of three teachers were also taught language features of genres when they were joining an English course. So, all teachers were still teaching language features of genres were influenced by their experience as language learners.

(2) Experience of what works best

All teachers had experienced what works best when they were teaching language features of genres on genre-based texts, such as Conditional Sentence, Recount, Narrative, and Descriptive. By experiencing of the way of teaching which works best, it could be predicted that the teachers would maintain their way of teaching and even improve it. So, the teachers' experience of what works best in teaching was also influence their beliefs.

(3) Personality factors

All teachers were already known about the condition of the class and the needs of the students since they had been teaching for years. Then, they believed that teaching language features of genres on K13 was still relevant. So, they kept teaching language

features of genres using drilling method in order to ease the way of learning English and giving them motivation to use English language for communication.

(4) Principles derived from an approach or method

All teachers believed that the implementation of K13 was really helpful for them to design the teaching and learning process and made the class more interactive. Although, they applied some steps on scientific approach which matched with the condition of the class and the students' need. So, since the teachers believed that the implementation of K13 was helpful and they applied them in teaching and learning process, their beliefs were influenced by the approach or method on the implemented curriculum.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings and discussion above, the conclusions of the research are explained as the following: (1) Teachers' beliefs toward teaching language features on K13. Teachers believed that they have to teach language features of genres to their students in consideration of fulfilling students' need to understand English language. They also believed that teaching languages features of genres can help students to understand English language and enables them to make correct sentences both grammatically and structurally. In teaching language features of genres, especially in Junior High School, the teachers can teach them the basic of language features, like Present, Past, Perfect in learning grammar. In teaching language grammar, the teachers believed that drilling is still relevant to help students to always remember the pronunciation of the words and to train them to keep trying to use the language. Then, the awareness of the teachers to fulfill the students' needs to understand and use the language, the teachers believed that they had to adjust the way of teaching due on the condition of the class in order to maintain the teaching and learning process.

(2) Teachers' practices toward teaching language features of genres on K13. In their teaching and learning process, all teachers mostly did the same activities in the classroom. They used only a textbook as the main guidance during teaching in the classroom. Then, in the classroom, all teachers were applying conventional teaching in

which the teachers were handling all the activities starting from the beginning up to the end of the lesson. Then, in the end of the lesson, the teachers did not guide the students to reflect what they had learned in that day as the goal of the implementation of K13.

(3) The factor which influenced teacher beliefs toward teaching language features of genres on K13. All teachers' practices were consistent to their beliefs as stated in the questionnaire. In fact, their beliefs were influenced by four sources of teachers beliefs. Firstly, teachers' beliefs were influenced by their experience as language learners. It can be interpreted from the interviews that when the subjects of the research were still in Junior and Senior High School, their teachers were teaching language features of genres and they were attracted toward their teaching practices. Therefore, the ways of their teaching were inspired from their teachers. Secondly, teachers' beliefs were influenced by their experience of what works best. It can be interpreted by the interviews that all three teachers had experienced what works best when they were teaching language features of genres on genre-based texts. Thirdly, teachers' beliefs were influenced by their personal factors. It can be interpreted that all teachers had been teaching for years and have already known about the condition of the class. So, they of their teaching was adjusted to their personal factors to fulfil the needs of the students. Forthly, teachers' beliefs were influenced by their principles which derived from an approach or method. It can be interpreted from the interviews that the implementation of K13 was helpful and the teachers applied them in teaching and learning process.

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